

MACHINE LEARNING-BASED PYROLYSIS CHARACTERIZATION IN CERAMIC-MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Thermoset polymers such as phenolic resins are commonly used as precursors for the ceramic matrix in carbon fiber-reinforced composites due to their high carbon yield in pyrolysis, and desirable thermal properties. Although the initial carbon content is inherent to the polymer, factors such as volatile release and pore structure evolution depend on reaction rates and phase transformations, both of which are strongly influenced by processing conditions. To better understand these complex correlations, it is essential to investigate and characterize the underlying kinetics of transformation, and their impact on property evolution during processing. Experimental data is typically used to establish these governing kinetics; however, accurate characterization remains challenging due to noisy and limited data, as well as the complexity and multiplicity of the reactions involved.

This paper presents a framework that combines machine learning and sparse regression with traditional model-based kinetic analysis to extract governing equations for the pyrolysis of a phenolic thermoset composite. The proposed approach follows three main steps: (1) estimation of activation energies and pre-exponential factors for a multistage process using traditional model-free analysis of thermogravimetric data; (2) prediction of reaction kinetics using a neural network with customized activation functions; and (3) model optimization using LASSO regularization to enforce sparsity, select key features, and reduce overfitting. This combined method improves interpretability and results in a simplified kinetic model that highlights dominant reaction mechanisms.

Applied to dynamic TGA data, the framework achieved strong predictive performance and produced interpretable kinetic expressions. Preliminary results from the in-house Python implementation demonstrate its potential as a promising alternative to traditional kinetic analysis, accurately capturing the kinetics of complex, multistage reactions, with reduced testing. By combining machine learning with sparse regression, this method enhances parameter estimation while offering a scalable and interpretable approach applicable across a range of thermal decomposition processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, fiber-reinforced composite materials have become increasingly popular across various industries due to their exceptional properties, including high specific strength and stiffness, and resistance to corrosion [1,2]. In particular, ceramic matrix composites are increasingly used in aerospace applications due to their unique combination of high thermal resistance, high strength, and low weight. Thermoset polymers like phenolic resins, for example, form three-dimensional networks through covalent bonding during curing. These crosslinked structures not only provide high thermo-mechanical properties but also exhibit desirable char-forming behavior during thermal decomposition, making them particularly well-suited for applications involving high-temperature exposure, such as ceramic-matrix composite manufacturing, where pyrolysis kinetics plays a critical role in determining the final material properties [3–6]. As a result, considerable effort has been devoted to understanding how processing conditions affect the underlying chemical reactions and, in turn, the resulting material behavior.

In recent years, advanced machine learning models, have emerged as valuable tools for studying high dimensional datasets to uncover underlying patterns, including the effect of processing conditions on material properties [7–9]. These data-driven methods are increasingly employed to uncover complex patterns in material behavior that are difficult to capture through traditional approaches. While conventional physics-based methods remain central to materials science, they often rely on simplifying assumptions, limiting their predictive capabilities in nonlinear, multistage processes [10]. As a result, there is growing interest in hybrid frameworks that integrate physical principles with machine learning to address these challenges, as well as improve generalization and enhance interpretability in complex systems [10].

Despite these advancements, significant challenges remain. For instance, qualification and certification of fiber-reinforced composite structures for aerospace applications still relies on extensive testing campaigns [8]. In the context of reaction kinetics, where understanding the rate and mechanism of chemical reactions under varying conditions is essential, this task is further hindered by the complexity and multiplicity of the reactions involved [5,11]. These limitations underscore the need for efficient, interpretable modeling approaches that can reduce experimental demands while still capturing the essential features of material behavior.

This work introduces a novel, theory-guided machine learning framework for analyzing the high-temperature pyrolysis stage in phenolic-based ceramic-matrix composites manufacturing. The proposed approach, NN-LASSO, integrates sparse regression, neural networks, and established kinetic theories to derive physics-based kinetic expressions from experimental data. The approach builds on the foundation of the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) method, extending its applicability to thermo-kinetic systems where overlapping mechanisms and limited data can hinder traditional modeling strategies [10,12]. Experimental data from thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is used to estimate kinetic parameters through the Friedman isoconversional analysis. These parameters, along with the extent of conversion, are used as inputs to train a neural network with custom activation functions representing candidate reaction mechanisms. Lasso regularization is then applied to enforce sparsity and improve model interpretability.

Preliminary results demonstrate the proposed framework's potential as a scalable alternative to traditional kinetic analysis. By integrating machine learning with sparse regression, the method enables improved parameter estimation while maintaining physical interpretability across multistage, nonlinear reaction systems.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Data Collection & Transformation

Experimental data used in this study was obtained from TGA tests conducted on cured carbon/phenolic composite samples. The composite was fabricated using a proprietary prepreg and processed into panels with a thickness of 0.64 cm ($\frac{1}{4}$ "), and a quasi-isotropic layup of $[(0/90)/(\pm 45)]_{8S}$. Lay-up and bagging were carried out according to the manufacturer's recommended procedures, and the laminates were cured in an autoclave following the manufacturer's recommended pressure and temperature cycles. Microstructural evaluation and density measurements showed results consistent with literature data for similar systems [5]. Samples were sectioned from the cured laminates and used for pyrolysis analysis via TGA. The test specimens had nominal dimensions of $0.2 \times 0.1 \times 0.64$ cm and weighed between 8–10 mg. All samples were obtained from the same composite batches and stored under consistent conditions to minimize variability [11].

TGA tests were performed using a TA Instruments TGA 550 under a nitrogen flow rate of 20 mL/min. Samples were placed in open platinum pans within a sealed chamber. Weight loss and weight loss rate were recorded throughout the pyrolysis process to assess thermal stability and extract kinetic information. Each run was conducted from room temperature up to 1000°C, followed by a 20-minute

isothermal hold before cooling. This temperature range was selected based on prior work establishing that the pyrolysis process in phenolic resins is typically complete by 800°C [13].

For data analysis, the extent of conversion, or degree of pyrolysis (α), was calculated from TGA results using normalized weight loss:

$$\alpha = (m_i - m_t)/(m_i - m_f) \quad (1)$$

where m_i is the initial mass, m_t is the mass at time t , and m_f is the final residual mass for each test [11,14,15].

For solid-state degradation reactions, the reaction rate is typically expressed as a function of the extent of conversion (α), rather than concentration. The general form of the rate equation:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T)f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

here $f(\alpha)$ describes the reaction mechanism and $k(T)$ is the temperature-dependent rate constant. According to the general form of the Arrhenius equation, the temperature dependency is commonly expressed as:

$$k(T) = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where A and E represent the pre-exponential factor and the activation energy, respectively [10,19]. The substitution of Eq. 3 in Eq. 2 gives:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) f(\alpha) \quad (4)$$

This rate expression is widely used in model-free and model-fitting approaches in thermal analysis [16]. In this study, the Friedman method was used to extract activation energies and pre-exponential factors from the TGA data [16,17]. These parameters, along with the calculated conversions, were used as inputs for the NN-LASSO framework.

2.2 NN-LASSO Framework for Kinetic Modeling

The NN-LASSO framework was developed to identify kinetic models from experimental data by combining neural networks, Lasso-based feature selection, and established pyrolysis kinetic theories. It builds upon the principles of the Sparse Identification of Nonlinear Dynamics (SINDy) method, which assumes that the temporal evolution of dynamic physical systems can be approximated by a sparse summation of nonlinear basis functions [10,12]. In this work, the governing reaction rate is expressed in the form:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i f_i(\alpha) \quad (5)$$

where $f_i(\alpha)$ are functions representing potential reaction mechanisms, and ω_i are trainable weights. The goal is to select a minimal subset of physics-based features that balances physical interpretability with sufficient accuracy in capturing the observed kinetics.

The experimental TGA data was first segmented into distinct temperature regions based on the observed weight-loss trends, with each segment corresponding to a different pyrolysis stage [11]. Activation energies and pre-exponential factors for each stage were calculated using the Friedman method and used as inputs to the model. A feature library was built from kinetic expressions commonly used to describe solid-state reactions, including functions of the form:

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (6)$$

$$f(\alpha) = \alpha^m \quad (7)$$

$$f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (8)$$

$$f(\alpha) = ((1 + \alpha)^n - 1)^p \quad (9)$$

Each function was implemented as a custom activation layer within the neural network, parameterized by m , n , and p , and constrained to remain within realistic kinetic ranges during training. Lasso regularization was then applied to the output layer to enforce sparsity by minimizing the L1 norm of the weights, driving non-essential terms to zero [18]. This promotes interpretability and reduces overfitting, resulting in a simplified expression composed of the most relevant kinetic mechanism. The Lasso penalty term is defined by:

$$\phi(\mathbf{w}) = \|\mathbf{w}\|_1 \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{w} = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)^n$ is the vector of trainable weights assigned to each feature in the output layer [18].

To optimize performance, a hyperparameter search was performed across regularization strengths, learning rates, batch sizes, and feature combinations. Multiple models were trained using randomly selected subsets of candidate functions. The final model was chosen based on its ability to match experimental trends while maintaining a minimal, interpretable form. **Fig. 1** presents a schematic of the three main steps of the framework.

Figure 1: Schematic of the proposed approach for kinetics modeling from experimental data using the NN-Lasso framework.

The framework was validated by comparing predicted reaction rates against experimental TGA results across dynamic and complex temperature cycles.

3 RESULTS

Based on TGA test data and reported results in the literature, three distinct temperature regions with peak degradation rates near 350°C, 550°C, and 600°C were identified for the studied material (**Fig.2a**) [11]. These correspond to crosslinking and chain scission reactions (300-440°C), followed by char formation and oxidation reactions (400-800°C) [13,15]. To focus on thermal degradation behavior, weight loss below 225°C, associated with polymerization and dewatering during curing, was excluded

from the analysis [19]. As summarized in **Table 1**, average activation energies of 195.5, 104.8, and 136.4 kJ/mol were calculated for these stages using Friedman's isoconversional method (**Fig.2b**) [11,20].

Figure 2: TGA derivative weight loss curves showing main degradation regions (a), and activation energy estimation using Friedman's analysis at various degrees of conversion (b).

Stage	Temperature Range ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Ea (kJ/mol)
1	300-430	195.5
2	430-600	104.8
3	600-900	136.4

Table 1: Kinetic parameters using Friedman analysis for different temperature ranges.

Following previous studies [21,22], the pyrolysis was modeled as a three-stage mechanism, with the rate expressions defined as:

$$\frac{d\alpha_1}{dt} = A_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,1}}{RT}\right) f(1 - \alpha_1)^{n_1} \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha_2}{dt} = A_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,2}}{RT}\right) f(\alpha_1 - \alpha_2)^{n_2} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha_3}{dt} = A_3 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,3}}{RT}\right) f(\alpha_2 - \alpha_3)^{n_3} \quad (13)$$

The overall conversion is expressed as:

$$\alpha(t) = w_1\alpha_1(t) + w_2\alpha_2(t) + w_3\alpha_3(t) \quad (14)$$

with $w_1 + w_2 + w_3 = 1$ and $0 < \alpha(t) < 1$.

To evaluate the NN-LASSO framework under different conditions, two models were trained using TGA data collected at heating rates of $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Training was performed over dynamic temperature cycles ranging from 225°C to 900°C . The mathematical expressions for the resulting kinetic models derived from the training process are presented in Eq. 28 and 29, respectively.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = 0.0016 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) x^{0.84} + 0.7 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) x^4(1-x)^2 + 0.13 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) x^{0.7}(1-x)^4 \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = 0.0223 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) x^{0.62}(1-x)^5 + 1.32 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) x^5(1-x)^{3.7} + 0.24 * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) ((1+x)^4 - 1)^5 \quad (16)$$

As shown in **Fig. 3** the predicted conversion rate curves closely matched experimental TGA results. The model trained on 2°C/min data achieved a R^2 value of 0.9703, while the 5°C/min model achieved $R^2 = 0.9634$. Although both models accurately captured the underlying kinetics, the differences in selected mechanisms and reaction orders across heating rates highlight the sensitivity of pyrolysis behavior to thermal conditions. These variations highlight the complexity of the pyrolysis process and the need for adaptable kinetic modeling approaches to accurately describe thermal degradation under different processing conditions.

Figure 3: Comparison of the conversion rate ($d\alpha/dt$) curve predicted for a 2°C/min (a) and a 5°C/min (b) dynamic cycle with that obtained from experimental results.

To further evaluate model performance under complex processing conditions, the NN-LASSO framework was trained on TGA data collected from a multi-step cycle, which included multiple heating ramps and isothermal holds (5°C/min to 550°C, followed by a 1-hour isothermal hold, and then 2°C/min to 1000°C). The model achieved an R^2 value of 0.9433. However, results shown in **Fig 4.b** reveal that the model struggled to accurately follow material behavior during the isothermal hold, suggesting that the current framework may benefit from incorporating additional variables or modifying the base equations.

Figure 4: Comparison of the (a) conversion extent (α), and (b) conversion rate ($d\alpha/dt$) curve predicted for a complex temperature cycle with that obtained from experimental results.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Accurate kinetic modeling of ceramic-matrix composites manufacturing remains a significant challenge, particularly during high-temperature processes like the pyrolysis stage. Predicting material behavior requires understanding the rate and mechanism of chemical reactions under varying thermal conditions, but this is often hindered by the complexity of multistage reactions and the limited, noisy nature of experimental data. These challenges highlight the need for efficient, interpretable modeling approaches that can capture the underlying kinetics while reducing experimental efforts.

Applied to the pyrolysis stage of ceramic-matrix composite manufacturing, the proposed machine learning-based framework demonstrated reliable performance in capturing overall reaction behavior using limited experimental data. By enforcing sparsity, the approach identified physics-based kinetic expressions, that are adaptable across different processing conditions.

While the balance between predictive accuracy and physical interpretability makes the NN-LASSO framework a promising tool for kinetic modeling, developing a single model that generalizes across all manufacturing scenarios remains a challenge. Incorporating physics-based constraints, could be a potential direction to address this challenge and support the development of a more robust machine learning framework. Future work will also focus on extending the application of this framework to other reaction kinetics and various thermally driven material transformations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rajak DK, Pagar DD, Menezes PL, Linul E. Fiber-reinforced polymer composites: Manufacturing, properties, and applications. *Polymers (Basel)* 2019;11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11101667>.
- [2] Rajak DK, Wagh PH, Linul E. Manufacturing technologies of carbon/glass fiber-reinforced polymer composites and their properties: A review. *Polymers (Basel)* 2021;13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13213721>.
- [3] Kausar A. Role of Thermosetting Polymer in Structural Composite. Issue 1 Kausar A *American Journal of Polymer Science & Engineering* 2017;5:1–12.
- [4] Sykes GF. NASA Technical Note: Decomposition Characteristics of a Char-Forming phenolic Polymer Used for Ablative Composites. Washington, D. C.: 1967.
- [5] Ko T-H. The Effect of Pyrolysis on the Mechanical Properties and Microstructure of Carbon Fiber-Reinforced and Stabilized Fiber-Reinforced Phenolic Resins for Carbon/ Carbon Composites. *Polym Compos* 1993;14.
- [6] Pulci G, Tirillò J, Marra F, Fossati F, Bartuli C, Valente T. Carbon-phenolic ablative materials for re-entry space vehicles: Manufacturing and properties. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2010;41:1483–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2010.06.010>.
- [7] Wagner N, Rondinelli JM. Theory-guided machine learning in materials science. *Front Mater* 2016;3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2016.00028>.
- [8] Zobeiry N, Reiner J, Vaziri R. Theory-guided machine learning for damage characterization of composites. *Compos Struct* 2020;246. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2020.112407>.
- [9] Pawar S, San O, Aksoylu B, Rasheed A, Kvamsdal T. Physics guided machine learning using simplified theories. *Physics of Fluids* 2021;33. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0038929>.
- [10] Bhadriraju B, Narasingam A, Kwon JS II. Machine learning-based adaptive model identification of systems: Application to a chemical process. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design* 2019;152:372–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cherd.2019.09.009>.
- [11] Portales Picazo P, Gray A, Zobeiry N. Efficient characterization and optimization of pyrolysis in carbon-carbon composites through machine learning. *Compos Part A Appl Sci Manuf* 2025;190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2024.108664>.
- [12] Brunton SL, Proctor JL, Kutz JN. Discovering governing equations from data by sparse identification of nonlinear dynamical systems. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2016;113:3932–7. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1517384113>.

- [13] Nam J-D, Seferis JC. Volatile Evolution in Thermoset Composites from Processing to Degradation. *Science and Engineering of Composite Materials* 1993;2. <https://doi.org/10.1515/SECM.1993.2.3.211>.
- [14] Trick KA, Saliba TE, Sandhu SS. A Kinetic Model of the Pyrolysis of Phenolic Resin in a Carbon/Phenolic Composite. *Carbon* N Y 1997;35:393–401.
- [15] Jiang H, Wang J, Wu S, Wang B, Wang Z. Pyrolysis kinetics of phenol-formaldehyde resin by non-isothermal thermogravimetry. *Carbon* N Y 2010;48:352–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2009.09.036>.
- [16] Aghili A, Shabani AH. A modification to the Friedman and Ortega isoconversional methods for evaluation of the activation energy as a function of conversion and temperature. *Thermochim Acta* 2024;736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2024.179748>.
- [17] Gong J, Gu Y, Zhai C, Wang Z. A hybrid pyrolysis mechanism of phenol formaldehyde and kinetics evaluation using isoconversional methods and genetic algorithm. *Thermochim Acta* 2020;690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2020.178708>.
- [18] Zhang H, Wang J, Sun Z, Zurada JM, Pal NR. Feature Selection for Neural Networks Using Group Lasso Regularization. *IEEE Trans Knowl Data Eng* 2020;32:659–73. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2019.2893266>.
- [19] Portales PP, Gray A, Zobeiry N. A Novel Framework for Accelerated Characterization of Pyrolysis Kinetics of High-Temperature Composites Using Theory-Guided Probabilistic Machine Learning. *Proceedings of the ASME 2023 Aerospace Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference, 2023*, San Diego, CA.
- [20] Muhammed F, Moretti L, Lavaggi T, Lam C, Tao T, Advani S, et al. Influence of pyrolytic decomposition on the microstructure evolution of benzoxazine-derived carbon–carbon composites. *J Mater Sci* 2022;57:21915–34. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-022-08007-9>.
- [21] Li C, Strachan A. Molecular scale simulations on thermoset polymers: A review. *J Polym Sci B Polym Phys* 2015;53:103–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/polb.23489>.
- [22] Zobeiry N, Humfeld KD. A physics-informed machine learning approach for solving heat transfer equation in advanced manufacturing and engineering applications. *Eng Appl Artif Intell* 2021;101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104232>.